

Facile Synthesis of Fluorine containing 1,3,5-Triarylpyrazoles and 3,5-Diarylisoxazoles

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Manuscript received 22 February 1988, accepted 29 July 1988

Fluorine containing 1,3-diarylchalcones on condensation with pentafluorophenylhydrazine in absolute ethanol, afforded the corresponding 1,3,5-triarylpyrazoles and with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine yielded 3,5-diarylisoxazoles. Fluorinated chalcones were synthesised by condensation of the appropriate acetophenones and aromatic aldehydes in aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution. All the compounds were characterised by their analytical and ir, ^1H nmr, ^{19}F nmr and mass spectral data. Mass fragmentation patterns of these compounds have also been discussed.

PYRAZOLES and isoxazoles are important nitrogen-containing heterocycles possessing diverse biological activities. Formycin, a naturally occurring C-nucleoside, has a pyrazole nucleus and exhibits antitumor, antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal properties. 5-Amino-4-cyano-1-pentafluorophenylpyrazole solution in water, sprayed post-emergence was reported to be effective in controlling *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Polygonum lapathifolium* etc. in rapeseed¹. Isoxazoles are useful as antiinflammatory², analgesic³, antipicornavirus⁴, antiviral⁴, antifungal⁵ and herbicidal⁶ agents. In view of the above findings, we now report the synthesis of several new bioactive heterocycles, viz. 1,3,5-triarylpyrazoles (2) and 3,5-diarylisoxazoles (3) via 1,3-diarylchalcones (1). Mass spectral studies of these compounds have also been discussed.

Scheme 1

Condensation of the appropriate fluorinated acetophenones and aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ethanolic sodium hydroxide yielded the corresponding fluorine containing 1,3-diarylchalcones (1). Chalcones possess an α,β -unsaturated

group and, therefore, activation exerted by the carbonyl group on the exocyclic double bond in these compounds renders them available for the addition of various amino compounds, viz. pentafluorophenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielding 1,3,5-triarylpyrazoles (2) and 3,5-diarylisoxazoles (3), respectively (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies: In the ir spectra of the compounds 1a-h, the carbonyl group absorbs at 1680 cm^{-1} . This down-field shift is due to conjugation of the carbonyl group with the olefinic double bond and aryl groups, which results in delocalisation of the electrons of carbonyl group giving ionic resonance structures. The olefinic bond absorbs at 1620 cm^{-1} . In the ^1H nmr of compounds 1a-h, the two olefinic protons constitute an AB system and appear as a pair of doublet; the down-field doublet centered at δ 7.94 due to CO-CH= and the doublet centered at δ 7.76 is due to CH=CH. This strong down-field shift of these two protons is characteristic of Aryl-CH=CHCO-Aryl system⁷. Aromatic protons appear as a multiplet at δ 6.9-8.2.

In the ir spectra of compounds 2a-g, the disappearance of signal at 1680 cm^{-1} indicates the absence of C=O group and formation of the desired compounds. Absorption bands at 1620 (C=N) and 1580 cm^{-1} (C=C) are also observed. In the ^1H nmr spectra of compounds 2a-h, a doublet centered at δ 7.13 for methine proton is observed. Aromatic protons appear as multiplet in the range δ 7.45-9.00. The ^{19}F nmr spectra show a sharp singlet at δ -110.10 ppm due to fluorine at 4-position of 3-phenyl ring. The pentafluorophenyl ring shows a doublet due to 2-F, 6-F, at δ -143.46 and -143.70 ppm, a triplet at δ -150.00, -150.23 and -150.52 ppm due to 4-F and a triplet due to 3-F, 5-F at δ -159.39, -159.62 and -159.85 ppm, respectively. Further confirmation of the formation

of the compounds was obtained by mass spectral data where molecular ion peaks M^+ at 404 (2a) and 438 (2b) correspond to their molecular masses. Compound 2a under electron impact provides a

molecular ion peak, M^+ , I at 404 (100%, base peak) (Scheme 2). $M+1$ and $M+2$ peaks are also observed at 405 and 406, respectively. The cation radical (I) further decomposes via four pathways:

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation pattern of 1-(2,9,4,5,6-pentafluorophenyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-phenylpyrazole.

TABLE 1—MAJOR MASS FRAGMENTS OF THE COMPOUNDS (2a AND 3a)

2a			3a		
Fragment no.	<i>m/z</i>	Relative intensity %	Fragment no.	<i>m/z</i>	Relative intensity %
I	<i>M</i> ⁺ 404	10.0	XII	181	25.0
II	385	10.0	XIII	148	15.0
III	329	7.5	XIV	207	10.0
IV	302	7.5	XV	290	22.0
V	291	43.7	XVI	123	55.0
VI	261	10.0	XVII	95	67.5
VII	131	37.5	XVIII	225	70.8
VIII	108	45.0	XIX	105	20.0
IX	77	62.5	XX	226	62.6
X	75	25.0	XXI	288	14.6
XI	234	12.5			
			I	<i>M</i> ⁺ 239	63.7
			II	118	5.0
			III	123	72.5
			IV	238	62.5
			V	89	5.0
			VI	95	22.5
			VII	143	5.0
			VIII	161	5.0
			IX	105	100
			X	77	50.0
			XI	51	17.5

(a), (b), (c) and (d). The major mass fragments with their relative intensities are recorded in Table 1.

The ir spectra of compounds 3a–g show the disappearance of signal at 1680 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of keto group present in the starting chalcone (1a–g). Additional absorption peaks are observed at 1610 (C=N) and 1570 cm⁻¹ (C=C). The ¹H nmr spectra of 3a–g show a doublet centered at δ 6.80 due to methine proton present at 4-position of the isoxazole nucleus. Aromatic protons appear as multiplet at δ 7.10–8.0. The ¹⁹F nmr spectra of the compounds show a sharp singlet at δ -110.62 ppm due to the presence of fluorine at 4-position of phenyl ring. Additional support is obtained from mass spectral data as molecular ion peaks *M*⁺ at 239 (3a) and 273 (3b) correspond to their molecular masses. Compound 3a under the influence of energetic electrons gives a molecular ion peak, *M*⁺, I, at 239 (63.7%) (Scheme 3). Cation radical I, further decomposes by three pathways: (a), (b) and (c). Benzoyl cation IX (*m/z* 105, 100%) forms the base peak. Major mass fragments of 3a with their relative intensities are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer at 89.9 MHz using TMS as internal standard, ¹⁹F nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol FX-90Q at 84.25 MHz using C₆F₆ as external standard, and mass spectra on Kratos 30 and 50 spectrometers. All the compounds were homogeneous on tlc in various solvent systems.

Pentafluorophenylhydrazine: A mixture of hexafluorobenzene (0.11 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.31 mol) and absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 12 h on a steam-bath. Excess of ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into water. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°), (58%) m.p. 77° (lit.⁸ 78°).

Scheme 3. Mass fragmentation pattern of 3-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-phenylisoxazole.

1,3-Diarylchalcones (1): The compounds were prepared following the method of Joshi *et al.*^{9,10}. A mixture of appropriate fluoroacetophenone (0.29 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.29 mol) was dissolved in a minimum amount of ethanol and then stirred at room temperature for 15 min. Sufficient 2 N NaOH was then added to it to render the solution alkaline and the whole reaction mixture was further stirred for ~ 0.5 h. It was then neutralised with 2 N HCl, diluted with water and left overnight. The precipitated chalcone was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow needles (Table 2). All the compounds were homogeneous on tlc in various solvent systems.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 1,3-DIARYLCHALCONES (1)

Compd. no.	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		δ (ppm)		
						C	H	N	C=O (s)	C=C (s)	OOH=	-OH=CH-	ArH
1a	4-F	H	67	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FO	79.63 (79.64)	4.85 (4.86)		1 680	1 620	7.94	7.76	6.90- 8.22
1b	4-F	2-Cl	81	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClFO	69.72 (69.90)	3.88 (3.88)		1 680	1 610	7.92	7.74	6.89- 8.21
1c	3-OH, 4-F	H	79	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FO	79.82 (80.00)	5.40 (5.41)		1 680	1 610	7.94	7.73	6.89- 8.24
1d	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	2-Cl	71	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClFO	69.72 (69.94)	4.37 (4.37)		1 680	1 620	7.93	7.75	6.90- 8.22
1e	5-OH, 2-F	2-Cl	85	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClFO	69.84 (69.94)	4.35 (4.37)		1 670	1 620	7.92	7.76	6.90- 8.22
1f	3-Cl, 4-F	H	73	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClFO	68.92 (69.09)	3.82 (3.83)		1 680	1 620	7.94	7.76	6.87- 8.11
1g	3-Cl, 4-F	2-Cl	85	63	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ FO	61.00 (61.01)	3.00 (3.05)		1 670	1 610	7.92	7.78	6.90- 8.24
1h	5-OH, 2-F	H	77	61	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FO	79.62 (80.00)	5.36 (5.41)		1 680	1 610	7.94	7.77	6.92- 8.24

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 1,3,5-TRIARYLPYRAZOLES (2)

Compd. no.	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		δ (ppm)		
						C	H	N	C=N (s)	C=O (s)	OH	ArH	OH ₂
2a	4-F	H	168	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₂	62.35 (62.37)	2.45 (2.47)	6.91 (6.93)	1 620	1 580	7.13	7.45-	—
2b	4-F	2-Cl	136	68	C ₂₁ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₂	57.43 (57.46)	2.05 (2.05)	6.34 (6.38)	1 620	1 570	7.0	7.46-	—
2c	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	H	142	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂	63.00 (63.15)	2.84 (2.87)	6.66 (6.69)	1 610	1 570	7.22	7.45-	2.3
2d	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	2-Cl	154	63	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ N ₂	58.31 (58.34)	2.43 (2.43)	6.11 (6.18)	1 610	1 570	7.15	7.42-	2.3
2e	5-OH, 2-F	2-Cl	156	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ N ₂	58.33 (58.34)	2.40 (2.43)	6.13 (6.18)	1 620	1 580	7.11	7.44-	2.1
2f	3-Cl, 4-F	H	154	71	C ₂₂ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₂	57.45 (57.46)	2.02 (2.08)	6.35 (6.38)	1 620	1 580	7.12	7.45-	—
2g	3-Cl, 4-F	2-Cl	161	68	C ₂₂ H ₉ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₂	53.25 (53.27)	1.65 (1.69)	5.90 (5.91)	1 620	1 570	7.14	7.47-	—

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3,5-DIARYLISOXAZOLES (3)

Compd. no.	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		δ (ppm)		
						C	H	N	C=N (s)	C=O (s)	OH	ArH	OH ₂
3a	4-F	H	158	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ FNO	75.29 (75.81)	4.15 (4.18)	5.82 (5.85)	1 610	1 570	6.80	7.10-	—
3b	4-F	2-Cl	152	63	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClFNO	65.62 (65.81)	3.26 (3.29)	5.09 (5.12)	1 610	1 570	6.82	7.20-	—
3c	3-OH, 4-F	H	147	66	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FNO	75.85 (75.88)	4.74 (4.74)	5.51 (5.53)	1 610	1 580	6.82	7.10-	2.2
3d	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	2-Cl	143	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClFNO	66.74 (66.78)	3.81 (3.82)	4.82 (4.87)	1 620	1 580	6.80	7.15-	2.2
3e	5-OH, 2-F	H	151	67	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FNO	75.83 (75.88)	4.71 (4.74)	5.49 (5.53)	1 620	1 580	6.80	7.10-	2.1
3f	3-Cl, 4-F	H	136	65	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClFNO	65.78 (65.81)	3.28 (3.29)	5.10 (5.12)	1 610	1 570	6.81	7.14-	—
3g	3-Cl, 4-F	2-Cl	154	62	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ FNO	58.43 (58.44)	2.56 (2.59)	4.52 (4.54)	1 610	1 570	6.81	7.10-	—

1,3,5-Triarylpiperazines (2) : A mixture of appropriate 1,3-diarylchalcone (1; 0.01 mol), pentafluorophenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) and piperidine (2–3 drops) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (50 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was

filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles (Table 3). All the compounds gave single spot in various solvent systems.

3,5-Diarylisoxazoles (4) : 1,3-Diarylchalcones (2; 0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01

mol) were dissolved in pyridine (25 ml) and refluxed on a sand-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was acidified with acetic acid and kept for 12 h at room temperature. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from alcohol as yellow crystals (Table 4). The compounds gave single spot in various solvent systems.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Ministry of Defence, Government of India, New Delhi, for financial support.

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